

Thermodynamics of the Interaction of Bivalent Transition Metal Ions with Xylenol Orange

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The formation constants, enthalpy and entropy changes for the formation of 1 : 1 chelates of bivalent transition metal ions with Xylenol Orange have been determined. The analysis of the thermodynamic quantities shows that two acetate groups, nitrogen and phenolic oxygen are coordinated to the metal.

INSPITE of the fact that 3,3'-bis-N-N'-di (carboxymethyl) amino methyl-*o*-cresol sulphothalein, popularly known as xylenol orange (DCAC), has been extensively used as an indicator¹⁻¹¹ or a reagent for the spectrophotometric determination¹²⁻²³ of a large number of metal ions, there exist differences in views regarding the nature of species in solution²⁴⁻²⁷ and the chelating sites in the reagent. Literature survey reveals that thermodynamic data on the interaction of DCAC with transition metal ions is meagre. In continuation of our recent study²⁸, we report thermodynamic parameters (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS values) and stability constants for the interaction of DCAC with bivalent Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn ions. These parameters have been used to elucidate information regarding the number and strength of bonds and also for detecting the changes in the structure of the complexes formed as a consequence of metal ions-DCAC interaction.

Experimental

Physical methods—as reported earlier²⁸.

Reagents and solutions—BDH (Analar) or equivalent quality chemicals were used for the preparation of the metal solutions. These were standardised by complexometric titrations. DCAC was purified as described by Muratami et al²⁹. Carbon dioxide free potassium hydroxide (Analar, BDH) solution standardised against standard oxalic acid was used for *pH*-metric titrations.

Methods—Keeping ionic strength constant at 1.0, 0.50, 0.25 and 0.10 with KNO_3 , the following sets of titrations (expanded scale *pH*-meter ECIL make was used throughout) were performed against standard KOH (0.025*M*) at $20 \pm 0.1^\circ$, $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $40 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

(i) For metal chelates

(a) 20.0 ml DCAC (0.001*M*) + 5.0 ml metal ion (0.001*M*) + 5.0 ml KNO_3 .

(b) 20.0 ml DCAC (0.001*M*) + 5.0 ml H_2O + 5.0 ml KNO_3 .

(ii) For ligand dissociation constant
(a) 25.0 ml $HClO_4$ (0.002*M*) + 25 ml H_2O vs 0.05, KOH.

(b) 25.0 ml $HClO_4$ (0.002*M*) + 25 ml DCAC (0.005*M*) vs 0.05*M*, KOH.

(c) 25.0 ml DCAC (0.005*M*) vs 0.05*M*, KOH.

Stability constants were then determined at four different ionic strengths by Bjerrum's method³⁰; from these an extrapolation to zero ionic strength was possible. Ligand dissociation constants were determined by the method of Irving and Rossotti³¹. The enthalpy change (ΔH) and entropy change (ΔS) were calculated from the temperature coefficient of the thermodynamic equilibrium constant for 1 : 1 metal ligand complex.

The accuracy for *pK* values reported in Table 1 is ± 0.02 log units and the accuracy of log *K* values given in Table 2 is ± 0.3 log units; therefore the precisions of ΔH and ΔS are ± 0.5 K cal. mole⁻¹ and ± 2 cal mole⁻¹ deg⁻¹.

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF DCAC IN 1.0*M*, 0.5*M*, 0.25*M* AND 0.1*M* KNO_3 AT 20°, 30° AND 40°.

Temp °C	Ionic strength	<i>pK</i> ₁	<i>pK</i> ₂	<i>pK</i> ₃	<i>pK</i> ₄	<i>pK</i> ₅
20	1.00 <i>M</i>	2.60	3.60	6.30	8.42	12.40
	0.50 <i>M</i>	2.60	3.60	6.28	8.35	12.32
	0.25 <i>M</i>	2.60	3.60	6.27	8.33	12.30
	0.10 <i>M</i>	2.60	3.60	6.25	8.31	12.20
30	1.00 <i>M</i>	2.55	3.50	6.24	8.30	12.15
	0.50 <i>M</i>	2.55	3.50	6.23	8.25	12.00
	0.25 <i>M</i>	2.55	3.50	6.22	8.24	11.95
	0.10 <i>M</i>	2.55	3.48	6.21	8.21	11.89
40	1.00 <i>M</i>	2.51	3.45	6.20	8.20	12.00
	0.50 <i>M</i>	2.51	3.45	6.17	8.13	11.78
	0.25 <i>M</i>	2.51	3.45	6.15	8.11	11.69
	0.10 <i>M</i>	2.51	3.41	6.13	8.00	11.59

Results and Discussion

The Job's method of continuous variation and Bjerrum's *pH*-metric method indicated the formation of 1 : 1 complex. The dissociation constants

(pK -values) for the ligand are given in Table 1. They are in fairly good agreement with the reported values²². Table 2 summarizes the values of log of thermodynamic formation constants at 20°, 30° and 40° for 1 : 1 metal ligand complexes along with the values of ΔH and ΔS .

The stability of the chelates $Mn(II) < Fe(II) < Co(II) < Ni(II) < Cu(II) > Zn(II)$ is in agreement with the Irving William rule. Plots of long K vs $1/T$ for the complexes gave a straight line indicating

in the pH range 1.7-5.8, 450 nm in the pH range 6.0-8.0, 570 nm in the pH range 8.5-9.5 and at 580 nm in the pH range 10.0-12.0. These changes in maxima in the case of different metal ions may also be attributed to the combination of metal ion with the dissociated phenolic group. The absorbance of the complexes remains almost constant in the pH ranges given for their formation and the values of $\bar{n} \approx 1$ was also obtained in these pH ranges which indicate the complete formation of 1 : 1 complex.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC STABILITY CONSTANTS (log K), ΔF , ΔH (in K cal mole⁻¹) AND ΔS (in cal mole⁻¹ deg.⁻¹) VALUES AT 30° FOR 1 : 1 METAL COMPLEXES OF DCAC.

Thermodynamic parameters	Temp. °C	Mn(II)	Fe(II)	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Zn(II)
log K	20	10.10	11.21	12.53	14.15	14.98	13.07
	30	10.00	11.10	12.41	14.00	14.81	12.95
	40	9.90	10.98	12.28	13.84	14.63	12.82
- ΔG	20	13.54	15.03	16.80	18.97	20.08	17.52
	30	13.86	15.39	17.90	19.41	20.53	17.95
	40	14.17	15.72	17.59	19.82	20.95	18.36
- ΔH		4.93	5.20	5.42	6.93	7.80	5.63
ΔS		31.91	34.88	39.80	42.60	43.53	41.94

that the heats of formation of these complexes were constant in the temp. interval 20°-40°. The obvious regularity seems to be in the entropy term ΔS , which decreases with increase of ionic radius. Further it appears that the stability of the DCAC complexes is mainly due to ΔS values which are large and positive, though the ΔH terms make contribution to the stability and there are variations in ΔH values.

The values of enthalpies increase from Mn(II) to Cu(II) with a drop at Zn(II). The contribution to the total enthalpy by the acetate groups is generally very small and sometimes endothermic as in metal carboxylate complexes involving malonate, succinate, acetate, etc. This contribution becomes still smaller in the case of bulky groups or rings because of steric hindrance. Thus the exothermic values given in Table 2 can only be accounted by metal-nitrogen and metal-phenolic oxygen bond. Secondly these values are more negative than the values reported for the complexes of iminodiacetic acid²³ where only two acetates and one nitrogen atom are coordinated with the metal. This also indicates the involvement of phenolic oxygen atom in coordination. This will produce a lack of charge on the site and lack of strain on the chelate ring. The mixtures containing metal and dye in the ratio of 1 : 1 gave the maxima at 578 nm in the pH range 6.7-7.1 for Mn(II), 500 nm in the pH range 5.4-6.6 for Fe(II), 578 nm in the pH range 5.8-6.1 for Co(II), 582 nm in the pH range 5.4-6.0 for Ni(II), 570 nm in the pH range 5.0-5.4 for Cu(II) and at 580 nm in the pH range 5.4-6.0 for Zn(II). The λ_{max} of the dye was found at 440 nm

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